

Disease resistance

Bacterial blight of rice appears to be indigenous on wild rice species in West Africa

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Bacterial blight (BB) of rice in West Africa was found in 1979 in the Sahel region of central Mali in an experiment station, but not in farmers' fields nor in wild rice populations. Unconfirmed reports of BB in introduced paddy rices in the dry areas of Senegal, Niger, and elsewhere in the West African savanna zone occur from time to time.

In September 1980, BB in Cameroun was confirmed on several Asian semi-dwarf varieties in an experimental nursery of the large rice project SEMRY I. The project is near Yagoua along the Logone River in the Sahel-Savanna zone at 10-1/2 degrees north latitude. BB was not detected in the wild annual *O. barthii* but it was found in one small

farmer's hydromorphic rice plot in the Mandara Mountains. This remote site 10 km SW of Mokolo near the Nigerian border was planted to a dryland variety resembling IRAT13 but neither the varietal name nor the seed source could be determined. So far as I am aware, this is the only known instance of BB in West Africa that is not connected with new Asian semidwarfs and with an irrigated paddy project.

Two areas were surveyed in September 1981 to further investigate the possibility of indigenous BB in wild rice or on farming sites: the Mandara foothills north, east, and southwest of Mokolo and the savanna area between Maroua and SEMRY II, 100 km to the northeast of Maroua.

Some hydromorphic dryland rice (*O. sativa*) mixed with *O. glaberrima* and old African dryland (possibly also some IRAT) cultivars is grown in the Mandara hills. No annual wild rice (*O. barthii*) was seen but the perennial *O. longistaminata* is present. No BB was

detected at any of the sites checked, not even in the same farmer's field where BB was found in 1980.

BB was found in many patches of wild *O. barthii* as well as in the less common *O. longistaminata* in the flat savanna NE of Maroua. These areas, near Longi and Bogu, have no native nor introduced rices. They are about 100 km away, without any river connection to the paddy rice project where BB was detected in 1980.

This is evidence that BB is indigenous in the savanna homeland of *O. barthii* and that it is maintaining itself on this annual species and on *O. longistaminata* without any connection to man. It is significant that BB is found only in dry areas similar to those where it has been found in cultivated rice. How widespread the indigenous presence of BB is in West Africa is not known, nor are any details of its epidemiological potential, ecology, off-season survival, or seed transmission. ■

Occurrence of sheath rot in Rajasthan

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Rice sheath rot caused by *Acrocylium drium oryzae* (revised as *Sarocladium oryzae*) was observed at the Rajasthan research station for the first time during the 1981 wet season. The disease was severe at panicle initiation stage in direct-seeded rainfed trials (UVT 1 and PVT 1) of the All India Coordinated Rice Improvement Project, Hyderabad. Rotting occurred at the upper leaf sheath enclosing young panicles. Oblong lesions on the flag leaf coalesced quickly and covered most of the sheath. The disease caused partial exsertion of the panicles, resulting in grain chaffiness. Powdery growth of the fungus was profuse inside affected leaf sheaths.

Infection in different varieties was calculated by counting infected and healthy panicles per unit area. Infected tillers were more than 50% in highly susceptible varieties and 15-20% in moderately susceptible varieties. Of 73 varieties, 7 showed a clearly susceptible reaction and 14 were moderately susceptible. The varieties and their reaction to sheath rot are:

Highly susceptible: CR141-7639, CRRP 2, IR9204-117-2-3-3-2, RP1422-2-1-2-3, RP1422-2-1-3-4, RP1422-2-2-3-2, RP1422-2-2-3-5, and KP1670-1418-2205-1582.

Moderately susceptible: CR222MW10, OR83-23, BK664, CR215-55-54-1, CR289-1208, RAU3-4-1, RP1674-4038-78-4, RP1899-1689-98, RP1899-1481-78-1, RP1451-1712-4319, RP1888-4254-1529-126, RP1670-4221-1585-2205-1418-3, Ad 98, and Rewa 353. ■

Phytoalexin production in the incompatible reaction of rice to *Pyricularia oryzae*

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The synthesis of antifungal compounds of phytoalexins by plants in response to incompatible races or species of fungal parasites is considered an important mechanism of resistance to fungal infection. Diterpenoid phytoalexins (momilactones A and B) have been isolated from blast-infected leaves of normally susceptible rice cultivar Sasashigure after treatment with 2,2-dichloro-3, 3-dimethylcyclopropane carboxylic acid. This fungicide is considered to activate natural resistance mechanisms, including an increased capacity to produce phytoalexins. ■

But until now, a phytoalexin response in the genetically based, cultivar- and race-specific resistance of rice to blast has not been reported. We have found that inoculation with avirulent blast races produced momilactone phytoalexins in genetically resistant cultivars.

After wound inoculation, leaf extracts were subjected to thin-layer chromatography and directly bioassayed by spraying the plate with spores of the green fungus *Cladosporium cucumerinum* (see figure). The white zones correspond to areas of inhibition of *C. cucumerinum*, showing the presence of phytoalexins. Although uninoculated tissue contains low levels of inhibitory compounds, the incompatible reaction clearly results in enhanced phytoalexin production,

TW TP RW RP mA
Cladosporium bioassay of leaf extracts of Tetep (T) and IR36 (R) inoculated with *Pyricularia oryzae* (P) or water (W). Momilactone A standard (mA) was included.

Momilactone production in rice with blast disease.

Isolate	Momilactone production	
	Tetep	IR36
2017	- (S)	+ (R)
750778	+ (R)	- (S)

^a- indicates negligible momilactone production, + indicates momilactone production. R = resistant, S = susceptible.

including the momilactones.

Two cultivars, Tetep and IR36, were tested with the isolates 2017 and 750778 (see table). Phytoalexin production is correlated with race- and cultivar-specific resistance. (This work was supported by a Ministry of Overseas Development, U. K., grant.) ■

Varietal resistance to kernel smut

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Kernel smut was first observed in a mild form on the variety Kannagi at Sundaraperumal koil and Swamimalai areas in Thanjavur district during 1975 kuruvai. In 1976, almost all varieties were affected. In Thanjavur delta, disease incidence in the kuruvai crop is heavy when monsoon rains are early. In 1981, incidence was severe.

Screening of 20 short-duration varieties and prerelease cultures assessed disease resistance. Four observations of 25 panicles per variety were made at 3-day intervals from the initial appearance of disease symptoms. The highest disease incidence for the four counts is given in the table. ■

Varietal resistance to kernel smut in Tamil Nadu, India.

Variety	Parentage	Kernel smut (%) (mean of 25 panicles)
ADT31	IR8/Cult 340	10.9
ADT34	IR8/Rodjolele	6.5
TKM9	TKM7/IR8	5.7
ADT36	Triveni/IR20	10.1
ADT33	IR8/Cult 340	6.3
IR50	Nam Sagui 19/IR2071-88//IR2061-214-3-6-2	0.0
Kannagi	IR8/TKM6	9.6
IET4786	CR10-114/CR115	1.8
AD16773	Ratna/ADT33	43.4
AD14018	AUT31/IE3125	3.1
AD14226	ADT30/CO 39	2.6
AD15426	IR30/IR28	0.0
AD14185	Pusa 140/Ratna	13.2
AD16674	ADT31/AD11585	0.0
AD14758	Ratna/AD11585	0.0
AD9246	ADT31/AD198	7.5
AD13887	ADT31/IR36	0.0
AD16586	Tiruvani/IR20//TKM6/IET2222	0.0
Pusa 186-10-4-5	Pusa 140-51///Amir//Sona/improved Sabarmathi	0.0
CO 33	IR8/ADT27	8.4

GENETIC EVALUATION AND UTILIZATION

Insect resistance

An improved method for field screening cultures resistant to brown planthopper

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To field evaluate at different sites rice cultures resistant to brown planthopper (BPH) *Nilaparvata lugens*, it has been necessary to develop methods to increase the BPH populations because populations are often too low or unevenly distributed. A modification of the method using resurgence-causing

insecticides is being successfully utilized at AICRIP (Hyderabad) and other sites in India.

Five border rows of a long-duration variety such as Mahsuri are close planted (10 × 10 cm). Within the border, 4 rows of 10 hills each of test varieties are alternated with 4 rows of a suscepti-